

Modelling galaxy emission-line kinematics using self-supervised learning

James Dawson

Cardiff University, The Parade, Cardiff CF24 3AA, Wales, UK

The 21-cm atomic Hydrogen (HI) line is often used by astronomers to study outermost regions of galactic discs (e.g., [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]). Marking the continuous boundary between galactic discs and their surrounding environments, measured rotation HI curves can be used to probe the properties of the dark matter halos within which galaxies are thought to reside. Within the disc, HI observations are useful in studying the gaseous content of galaxies as well as allowing astronomers to analyse the kinematic properties of substructures such as bars, warps, counter-rotating discs, and star-forming spiral arms (e.g., [6, 7, 8, 9]). Complementary observations of molecular gas (typically the CO molecule) can reveal the interplay between these gas phases and allows astronomers to build a more complete kinematic profile of galaxies. HI, typically being largely extended, allows astronomers to trace environmental properties such as extended tidal features and the existence of dwarf companions [3, 4, 5, 10, 11, 12], whereas CO is typically more centrally located within galactic discs, allowing astronomers to get a handle on the influence of central black holes on the disc kinematics (e.g., results from the mm-Wave Interferometric Survey of Dark Object Masses –WISDOM– project).

The study of HI with adequate spatial and spectral resolution, requires the use of interferometers. Current state of the art interferometers collect raw data products of enormous size, and next generation interferometers are set to only be more powerful and data-hungry. Currently it is estimated that the **S**quare **K**ilometre **A**rray (SKA) will collect data on the order of hundreds of petabytes per year. This firmly pushes astronomy into the *big data era*. These kinds of data sizes are too large to exploit by hand, and are even too large to store. Therefore, astronomers should be looking to embrace a paradigm shift in which real-time models capable of efficient science are tested and deployed on incoming data. In this way physical information would be extracted from incoming data automatically, leaving the work of unravelling the prevailing science to astronomers.

A self-supervised, physics-aware, Bayesian, neural network

To this end we have developed a novel machine learning model with the primary goal of inferring the kinematic properties of gas discs in galaxies and an emphasis on extracting (simplistic) characteristics of their rotation curves. In the past decade, machine learning (ML) has become a popular solution to many *big data* challenges in galaxy evolution studies, but remains an under-utilised resource among the galaxy kinematics community. In previous work [13], we sought to address this us-

ing more conventional ML approaches. However, while conventional ML models are capable of high empirical accuracy and low testing time (e.g., [14, 15]), they are often plagued by slow training times [16] and, in some cases, poor generalisation to unseen data-sets [17, 18]. For next generation instruments like the SKA, where data cannot be efficiently stored, these qualities are unsuitable and therefore we look to use alternative methods which incorporate the benefits of ML, without the drawbacks associated with standard ML practice.

Figure 1: A simplified pictorial representation of the neural network used in this work. The model features two convolutional encoder subnets which concatenate learned features before passing them to a decoder subnet. The model receives moment maps as inputs and minimises the loss between decoder-generated moment map outputs and the inputs throughout training. In the diagram grey squares indicate convolutional layers, blue rectangles depict linearly connected layers, and the grey cube represents the auxiliary 3D cube containing the coordinate axes passed into the network.

The approach we turn to is *self-supervised learning*, whereby models train themselves, without the need for a labelled training set. This has huge benefits in that one no longer requires long training times on throw-away datasets, essentially eliminating data wastage completely. Few examples of physics-aware self-supervised learning approaches exist in astronomy (e.g., [19]) and, until now, none exist in the context of modelling galaxy kinematics.

The model itself, (shown in Figure 1), is a branched convolutional autoencoder. The encoder subnets extract lower dimensional feature representations from input images. In this case, as we are focused on models capable of working with interferometric data products, these are integrated intensity and mean velocity maps. Features are extracted from the maps using a combination of convolutional and linearly connected layers. The decoder then reconstructs the input images from the learned feature embeddings passed forward from the center of the

network. In a standard convolutional autoencoder, the decoder would make use of transposed convolution operations, however in this network the decoder is composed of analytical functions written using native PyTorch. By imposing this constraint, the CAE is forced to generate semantic encodings of the input images to pass to the decoder. In this way, we can be assured that the encoders are learning semantically meaningful properties of the input images and are no longer tied to traditional training methods, instead allowing the network to train on all available data (including test data) in a self-supervised manner. The model becomes *physics-aware* once the decoder functions are chosen as to reveal physically meaningful information about the input. For this work, the physics-awareness of the model refers to our focus on parameterising rotation curves and intensity profiles of galaxies. Therefore, our decoder functions explicitly take variables which describe these qualities.

Application to interferometric data

As part of our analysis, we tested the model by training on 17 galaxies observed using the Very Large Array (VLA) as part of The HI Nearby Galaxy Survey (THINGS) [20]. An example galaxy from this selection (NGC 2403) is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: NGC 2403, observed in HI and evaluated using the neural network model. The black dashed lines and grey areas show the mean and 1σ modelling errors respectively for profiles predicted by the neural network model. The blue dashed line shows a major axis cut of the input intensity map. The red dashed line and filled area show the best fit and associated errors modelled using BBAROLO. The network predicted parameters are shown as text in the subplots.

In order to demonstrate the flexibility of this network architecture, we trained a model to recover the kinematic properties of CO line emission discs using the Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA). Six galax-

Figure 3: NGC 1387, observed in CO and evaluated using the neural network model. Figure style and layout matches that of Figure 2, with KinMS used for modelling comparison.

ies drawn from the WISDOM project, with high ‘spatial resolution’, were trained and tested on using our model.

Figures 2 and 3, show that the model is suitable for recovering rotation curves of galaxies from their kinematics. As well as removing the problem of throw-away training data-sets, our approach also overcomes the common issues associated with transfer learning when attempting to build practical models. The model architecture and training style presented in this work can be applied to a multitude of different data-sets with the possibility of architectural modifications suiting other types of data outside of interferometry (e.g., IFU data) and even astronomy.

References

- [1] Warren, B. E., et al. 2004, AJ, 128, 1152
- [2] Begum, A., et al. 2005, A&A, 433, 1
- [3] Sancisi, R., et al. 2008, A&ARv, 15, 189
- [4] Heald, G., et al. 2011, A&A, 526, 118
- [5] Koribalski, B. S., et al. 2018, MNRAS, 478, 1611
- [6] Józsa, G. I. G., et al. 2007, A&A, 468, 731
- [7] Spekkens, K., & Sellwood, J. A. 2007, ApJ, 664,204
- [8] Kamphuis, P., et al. 2015, MNRAS, 452, 3139
- [9] Di Teodoro, E. M. & Fraternali, F., 2015, MNRAS, 451, 3021
- [10] Hibbard, J. E., et al. 2001, ApJ, 122, 2969
- [11] Serra, P., et al. 2013, MNRAS, 428, 370
- [12] Bosma, A. 2016, Proc. IAU Symp., 220, 11
- [13] Dawson, J. M., et al. 2019, MNRAS, 491, 2506
- [14] Breiman, L. 2001, Machine Learning, 45, 5
- [15] Krizhevsky, A., et al. 2012, ANIPS, 25, 1097
- [16] Lim, T.-S., et al. 2000, Machine Learning 40, 203
- [17] Dinh, L., et al. 2017, eprint:arXiv:1703.04933
- [18] Kawaguchi, K., et al. 2017, eprint:arXiv:1710.05468
- [19] Aragon-Calvo, M. A., & Carvajal, J. C. 2020, MNRAS, 498, 3713
- [20] Walter, F., et al. 2012, ApJ, 136, 2563

Short CV

2013-2016: BSc in Astrophysics, Cardiff University, UK
 2016-2017: MSc in Astrophysics, Cardiff University, UK
 2017-present: PhD in Data Intensive Astrophysics, Cardiff University, UK